

BIOPOLE Ny Ålesund CTD and water sampling report

Kate Hendry
British Antarctic Survey

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Summary

A total of 9 successful CTD casts were undertaken using the NERC Arctic Station CTD frame. The unit consists of a SeaBird SBE 19+ V2 CTD (a pumped system), and additional sensors for chlorophyll fluorescence, particle scattering, and photosynthetically active radiation (PAR).

Between casts the CTD frame and sensors were washed in freshwater; the conductivity cell flushed through three times and then stored kept in clean tap water. Before longer term storage, the CTD was rinsed again in tap water, and the conductivity cell flushed three times and stored in Milli-Q water. The conductivity cell was not cleaned in dilute bleach or Triton-X, and the recommendation is that this cleaning procedure is carried out before the next use.

The deepest cast was 345m, and the shallowest cast was 46m.

Instrument payload

The following sensors were installed on the CTD frame:

Parameter	Serial number
Temperature	8139
Conductivity	8139
Pressure (strain gauge)	870 psia S/N 11918058
Fluorometer	FLBBRT-6905
Photosynthetically active radiation (PAR)	2148

Instrument configuration

Example status report:

```
SBE 19plus V 3.1.8 SERIAL NO. 8139 25 Jul
2023 06:54:56
vbatt = 12.4, vlith = 8.5, ioper = 62.2 ma,
ipump = 62.9 ma,
iext01 = 32.8 ma, iext2345 = 15.9 ma
status = not logging
number of scans to average = 1
samples = 12181, free = 3858298, casts = 2
mode = profile, minimum cond freq = 3094, pump
delay = 60 sec
autorun = no, ignore magnetic switch = no
battery type = alkaline, battery cutoff = 7.5
volts
```

```
pressure sensor = strain gauge, range = 870.0
SBE 38 = no, WETLABS = no, OPTODE = no, SBE63 =
no, SeaFET = no, Gas Tension Device = no
Ext Volt 0 = yes, Ext Volt 1 = yes
Ext Volt 2 = yes, Ext Volt 3 = no
Ext Volt 4 = no, Ext Volt 5 = no
echo characters = yes
output format = raw HEX
```

The battery remained above 12V and was not replaced.

The Seasave Instrument Configuration file used for all casts was 19-8139.xmlcon.

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<SBE_InstrumentConfiguration SB_ConfigCTD_FileVersion="7.26.4.0" >
  <Instrument Type="11" >
    <Name>SBE 19plus V2 Seacat CTD</Name>
    <PressureSensorType>1</PressureSensorType>
    <ExternalVoltageChannels>3</ExternalVoltageChannels>
    <Mode>0</Mode>
    <!-- Serial RS-232 Sensor: 0 = None. -->
    <SerialRS232C_Sensor>0</SerialRS232C_Sensor>
    <SampleIntervalSeconds>60</SampleIntervalSeconds>
    <ScansToAverage>1</ScansToAverage>
    <SurfaceParVoltageAdded>0</SurfaceParVoltageAdded>
    <ScanTimeAdded>0</ScanTimeAdded>
    <NmeaPositionDataAdded>0</NmeaPositionDataAdded>
    <NmeaDepthDataAdded>0</NmeaDepthDataAdded>
    <NmeaTimeAdded>0</NmeaTimeAdded>
    <NmeaDeviceConnectedToPC>0</NmeaDeviceConnectedToPC>
    <SensorArray Size="6" >
      <Sensor index="0" SensorID="58" >
        <TemperatureSensor SensorID="58" >
          <SerialNumber>8139</SerialNumber>
          <CalibrationDate>19-Aug-21</CalibrationDate>
          <A0>1.27290955e-003</A0>
          <A1>2.73531459e-004</A1>
          <A2>-1.43103676e-006</A2>
          <A3>1.92848631e-007</A3>
          <Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
          <Offset>0.0000</Offset>
        </TemperatureSensor>
      </Sensor>
      <Sensor index="1" SensorID="3" >
        <ConductivitySensor SensorID="3" >
          <SerialNumber>8139</SerialNumber>
          <CalibrationDate>19-Aug-21</CalibrationDate>
          <UseG_J>1</UseG_J>
          <!-- Cell const and series R are applicable only for wide range sensors. -->
```

```
<SeriesR>0.0000</SeriesR>
<CellConst>2000.0000</CellConst>
<ConductivityType>0</ConductivityType>
<Coefficients equation="0" >
  <A>0.00000000e+000</A>
  <B>0.00000000e+000</B>
  <C>0.00000000e+000</C>
  <D>0.00000000e+000</D>
  <M>0.0</M>
  <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>
</Coefficients>
<Coefficients equation="1" >
  <G>-1.01578936e+000</G>
  <H>1.51653733e-001</H>
  <I>-3.85203048e-004</I>
  <J>5.22823743e-005</J>
  <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>
  <CTcor>3.2500e-006</CTcor>
  <!-- WBOTC not applicable unless ConductivityType = 1. -->
  <WBOTC>0.00000000e+000</WBOTC>
</Coefficients>
<Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
<Offset>0.00000</Offset>
</ConductivitySensor>
</Sensor>
<Sensor index="2" SensorID="46" >
  <PressureSensor SensorID="46" >
    <SerialNumber>8139</SerialNumber>
    <CalibrationDate>11-Aug-21</CalibrationDate>
    <PA0>2.51958672e+000</PA0>
    <PA1>2.64333457e-003</PA1>
    <PA2>1.79105062e-011</PA2>
    <PTEMPA0>-7.34437919e+001</PTEMPA0>
    <PTEMPA1>4.63590679e+001</PTEMPA1>
    <PTEMPA2>3.28029126e-001</PTEMPA2>
    <PTCA0>5.24270996e+005</PTCA0>
    <PTCA1>6.10037698e+001</PTCA1>
    <PTCA2>-8.64550164e-001</PTCA2>
    <PTCB0>2.51086250e+001</PTCB0>
    <PTCB1>-4.75000000e-004</PTCB1>
    <PTCB2>0.00000000e+000</PTCB2>
    <Offset>0.000000</Offset>
  </PressureSensor>
</Sensor>
<Sensor index="3" SensorID="20" >
  <FluoroWetlabECO_AFL_FL_Sensor SensorID="20" >
    <SerialNumber>FLBBRT-6905</SerialNumber>
```

```

    <CalibrationDate>6/16/21</CalibrationDate>
    <ScaleFactor>6.00000000e+000</ScaleFactor>
    <!-- Dark output -->
    <Vblank>0.0680</Vblank>
  </FluoroWetlabECO_AFL_FL_Sensor>
</Sensor>
<Sensor index="4" SensorID="70" >
  <TurbidityMeter SensorID="70" >
    <SerialNumber>FLBBRT-6905</SerialNumber>
    <CalibrationDate>6/16/21</CalibrationDate>
    <ScaleFactor>1.684e-006</ScaleFactor>
    <!-- Dark output -->
    <DarkVoltage>4.700e+001</DarkVoltage>
  </TurbidityMeter>
</Sensor>
<Sensor index="5" SensorID="76" >
  <PARLog_SatlanticSensor SensorID="76" >
    <SerialNumber>2148</SerialNumber>
    <CalibrationDate>4/28/21</CalibrationDate>
    <a0>9.9401e-001</a0>
    <a1>8.0874e-001</a1>
    <Im>1.3589e+000</Im>
    <ConversionUnits>1</ConversionUnits>
    <Multiplier>1.0000e+000</Multiplier>
  </PARLog_SatlanticSensor>
</Sensor>
</SensorArray>
</Instrument>
</SBE_InstrumentConfiguration>

```

Note that the calibration file does not contain the correct coefficients for the scattering data. The calibration is carried out in two modes: counts and voltages. The coefficients in the calibration file are set for the 'counts' version, when it needs to be the 'voltages' version. In order to correct this, the following equations were used in post-processing (see below):

$$bb_{voltage} = \left(\frac{bb_{output}}{1.684e-6} \right) + 47$$

$$bb_{corr} = (bb_{voltage} - 0.061) \times 1.384$$

Where $bb_{voltage}$ is the raw voltage value from the sensor, bb_{output} is the uncorrected data in your .cnv file, and bb_{corr} is the corrected bb value. Note that bb is the volume scattering function (in $m^{-1} sr^{-1}$) and needs further processing to produce the particle optical backscattering (in m^{-1}). The range of bb that can be measured by this unit is 0-5 $m^{-1} sr^{-1}$ and the sensor became saturated in the inner fjord due to the cloudiness of the water.

CTD operation

The CTD casts were carried out either from the Polarcirkel workboat or the King's Bay R/V *Teisten*. The frame was lowered and raised either using a hand-winch system (Polarcirkel) at approximately 0.5m/s, or via an electric winch system (*Teisten*) at approximately 1m/s. The CTD was lowered in a continuous movement, but rate of recovery likely varied, especially with the hand-winch system.

An initial soak of 3 minutes at 5m water depth was carried out, before winching the frame to the surface and lowering to within approximately 10m of the seafloor, with depth recorded from the onboard echosounder.

Note it was not feasible to collect samples for salinity calibration purposes.

There were no major technical issues with the CTD suite, and no instruments required changing for spares.

Cast summary

Stn	Vessel	Date	Depth (m)	Lat (N)	Lon (E)	Comments	Filename
KB2	PolarCirkel	22/07/23	300	78° 58.644	11° 43.838	Test cast for CTD data	SBE19plus_01908139_2023_07_22_0001.hex
KB5	PolarCirkel	23/07/23	80	78° 53.787	12° 25.345	Chl worked; bb saturated; otherwise good	SBE19plus_01908139_2023_07_23_0001.hex
KB4	PolarCirkel	23/07/23	104	78° 54.639	12° 11.808	Chl worked; turb partially saturated; otherwise good	SBE19plus_01908139_2023_07_23_0002.hex
KB2	PolarCirkel	23/07/23	290	78° 58.644	11° 43.838	Good	SBE19plus_01908139_2023_07_23_0003.hex
KB3	PolarCirkel	24/07/23	340	78° 57.295	11° 57.134	Good	SBE19plus_01908139_2023_07_24_0002.hex
KB6	PolarCirkel	25/07/23	49	78° 55.792	12° 23.146	Chl worked; turb partially saturated; otherwise good	SBE19plus_01908139_2023_07_25_0001.hex
KB7	PolarCirkel	25/07/23	60	78° 57.985	12° 22.798	Chl worked; turb partially saturated; otherwise good	SBE19plus_01908139_2023_07_25_0002.hex
KB1	Teisten	27/07/23	345	79° 00.701	11° 25.602	Good	SBE19plus_01908139_2023_07_27_0001.hex
KB8	Teisten	27/07/23	48	78° 52.772	12° 31.067	Chl worked; turb partially saturated; otherwise good	SBE19plus_01908139_2023_07_27_0002.hex

The cast at KB2 was repeated to obtain fluorometry data. There was also a test cast to 10m near the harbour on 21/7/23. The data from the test casts at the harbour and KB2 were not fully processed.

Total veer 1616m

Total haul 1616m

CTD data processing

Standard Sea-Bird processing of the raw data was completed using Sea-Bird Data Processing software.

The processing order used was:

- Data Conversion
- MATLAB plot Pressure vs Time to confirm no major spikes
- Filter 0.15s on conductivity and pressure
- CellTM
- Loop Edit velocity limit=0 with remove surface soak.
- Derive depth (latitude 79°N), salinity, and density (sigma-theta)
- Bin Average in depth down cast only 1m bins
- MATLAB conversion to .mat
- Post-processing of backscatter data (see comment above)
- MATLAB saving of .mat and .csv files

Photic zone depth was calculated by fitting a curve to $\ln(\text{PAR})$ vs. depth, and ranged from 2 to 25m:

Station number	Photic Zone Depth (m)
1	21
2	25
3	12
4	15
5	5
6	3
7	7
8	2

Plots for quality control checks:

Profile plots:

KB1

KB2

KB3

KB4

KB5

KB6

KB7

KB8

Plots of photic zone depth by station:

MATLAB code for CTD processing

```
% Code for plotting BIOPOLE CTD data
% K Hendry July 19th 2023
%
% This script extracts (*_bin.cnv and) *_der.cnv data for each station
% saves as .mat, and plots up profiles
%
% Note that you need cnv2mat.m to run this script
%

close all
clear all

%% Enter station name here
station = 'BIOPOLE_KB1';

open_name = strcat(station, '_bin.cnv');

[lat,lon,gtime,data,names,sensors]=cnv2mat(open_name);

% This is the structure of the data file
% # name 0 = scan: Scan Count
% # name 1 = prdM: Pressure, Strain Gauge [db]
% # name 2 = tv290C: Temperature [ITS-90, deg C]
% # name 3 = c0S/m: Conductivity [S/m]
% # name 4 = flECO-AFL: Fluorescence, WET Labs ECO-AFL/FL [mg/m^3]
% # name 5 = par/sat/log: PAR/Logarithmic, Satlantic [umol photons/m^2/sec]
% # name 6 = turbWETbb0: Turbidity, WET Labs ECO BB [m^-1/sr]
% # name 7 = sigma-é00: Density [sigma-theta, kg/m^3]
% # name 8 = depSM: Depth [salt water, m], lat = 79
% # name 9 = potemp090C: Potential Temperature [ITS-90, deg C]
% # name 10 = sal00: Salinity, Practical [PSU]
% # name 11 = flag: flag

%% Correct the backscatter measurements

% Note - this corrects the calibration error in the .xmlcon file giving bb,
% which is the volume scattering function in m-1 sr-1
% Can use beta_to_bbp.m to convert further into bbp in m-1

b = (data(:,7)/1.684e-6)+47;
bb = (b-0.061)*1.384;
% note that the calibration file says this parameter should be 1.384e-3,
```

```
% but I think this is out by a factor of 1000

% temperature = data(:,3);
% salinity = data(:,11);
% lambda = 700;
%
% bbp = beta_to_bbp(bb,temperature,salinity,lambda);
%
% clearvars temperature salinity lambda
```

```
clearvars b
```

```
%% Plot up the data
```

```
figure
```

```
subplot(2,3,1)
plot(data(:,3),data(:,9),'bo')
xlabel('Temperature (^oC)')
ylabel('Depth (m)')
set(gca, 'YDir','reverse')
```

```
subplot(2,3,2)
plot(data(:,11),data(:,9),'bo')
xlabel('Salinity')
ylabel('Depth (m)')
set(gca, 'YDir','reverse')
```

```
subplot(2,3,3)
plot(data(:,5),data(:,9),'bo')
xlabel('Fluorescence (mg/m^3)')
ylabel('Depth (m)')
set(gca, 'YDir','reverse')
```

```
subplot(2,3,4)
plot(data(:,6),data(:,9),'bo')
xlabel('PAR (umol photons/m^2/s)')
ylabel('Depth (m)')
set(gca, 'YDir','reverse')
```

```
subplot(2,3,5)
plot(bb,data(:,9),'bo')
xlabel('BB (m^-1/sr)')
ylabel('Depth (m)')
set(gca, 'YDir','reverse')
```

```

subplot(2,3,6)
plot(data(:,8),data(:,9),'bo')
xlabel('Sigma-theta (kg/m^3)')
ylabel('Depth (m)')
set(gca, 'YDir','reverse')

%% Save .mat file and plot figure

save_name = strcat(station, '.mat');
save(save_name)
saveas(gcf,station,'jpeg')
save_name = strcat(station, '.csv');
newdata = [data bb];
writematrix(newdata,save_name)

% END

%% Calculate photic zone depth - fit exponential curve to top 100m PAR data
% *****

clear all
close all

%% Enter station name here
station = ('BIPOLE_KB1');

open_name = strcat(station, '_bin.csv');

[lat,lon,gtime,data,names,sensors]=cnv2mat(open_name);

% Enter depth of interest

n = 30;

% Get data for top 100m only

par_day_100 = data(1:n,6);
y = data(1:n,9);

% Calculate photic zone depth

I = log(0.01);

for lpJ = 1:n
    ln_E(lpJ,1) = log(par_day_100(lpJ,1));

```

```
end
```

```
c = polyfit(ln_E,y,1);
```

```
figure
```

```
plot(ln_E,y)
```

```
set(gca, 'Ylim', [0 100])
```

```
set(gca, 'YDir','reverse')
```

```
ylabel('Depth (m)')
```

```
xlabel('ln(E)')
```

```
q = c(1,1);
```

```
PZD = abs(l.*q);
```

```
% END
```

Water sampling

Seawater samples were collected from 5m, 30m and bottom waters where possible using a 2.5L Niskin bottle (Polarcirkel) or 10L Niskin bottle (*Teisten*). The valves and caps were checked before deployment. The bottle was deployed using the same winch system as for the CTD, with an added weight attached to the shackle in each case. The bottles were fired using a messenger system. Note that there were several failed attempts at firing the bottle from the Polarcirkel, because the messenger did not attach fully to the wire (the messenger provided by Hendry) or because the messenger did not hit the trigger bar (the messenger from the UK Arctic Station), and it is recommended for a new messenger to be purchased for the next use.

The bottles were recovered to the boat in each case, and immediately sampled for nutrients, filtering through a 0.8/0.2 μm Acrodisk filter into an acid-cleaned plastic bottle. The nutrient samples were not filtered at KB2. Unfiltered samples were then taken for oxygen isotopes, total phosphorus, total metals, particle cytometry and phytoplankton cell counts. The remaining seawater was collected in an acid-rinsed 1L amber plastic bottle for later processing. Note that for KB8, the seawater was sampled only into the 1L amber plastic bottles and all filtering and subsampling happened later in the laboratory.

In the laboratory, the nutrients samples were frozen immediately at -20°C . The phytoplankton cell count samples were fixed with 1ml lugols and parafilm. The oxygen isotope samples were sealed with electrical tape. Water samples were filtered through GFFs for particulate organic carbon and nitrogen (POC/PON) and through 0.8 μm polycarbonate filters for reactive silica. Note that for two samples, additional 100ml samples were filtered through both polycarbonate and cellulose acetate filters for cross comparison of filter types for reactive silica. Some remaining water was assessed for dissolved organic carbon content when feasible.

Table of water sampling events:

Stn	Vessel	Date	Depth (m)	Lat (N)	Lon (E)	Notes	Salinity
KB2	PolarCirkel	22/07/23	200	78° 58.644	11° 43.838	Unfiltered samples for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, nuts, TP, cyto, lugols, tot metals	34.9
KB2	PolarCirkel	22/07/23	5	78° 58.644	11° 43.838	Unfiltered samples for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, nuts, TP, cyto, lugols, tot metals	32.8
KB5	PolarCirkel	23/07/23	80	78° 53.787	12° 25.345	Unfiltered samples for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, TP, cyto, lugols, tot metals; filtered nuts	34.7
KB5	PolarCirkel	23/07/23	30	78° 53.787	12° 25.345	Unfiltered samples for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, TP, cyto, lugols, tot metals; filtered nuts	34.1
KB5	PolarCirkel	23/07/23	5	78° 53.787	12° 25.345	Unfiltered samples for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, TP, cyto, lugols, tot metals; filtered nuts	31.3
KB4	PolarCirkel	23/07/23	100	78° 54.639	12° 11.808	Unfiltered samples for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, TP, cyto, lugols, tot metals; filtered nuts	34.8
KB4	PolarCirkel	23/07/23	30	78° 54.639	12° 11.808	Unfiltered samples for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, TP, cyto, lugols, tot metals; filtered nuts	34.3
KB4	PolarCirkel	23/07/23	5	78° 54.639	12° 11.808	Unfiltered samples for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, TP, cyto, lugols, tot metals; filtered nuts	32
KB2	PolarCirkel	23/07/23	30	78° 58.644	11° 43.838	Unfiltered samples for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, nuts, TP, cyto, lugols, tot metals	34.2
KB3	PolarCirkel	24/07/23	5	78° 57.295	11° 57.134	Unfiltered samples for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, TP, cyto, lugols, tot metals; filtered nuts	31.8

KB3	PolarCirkel	24/07/23	200	78° 57.295	11° 57.134	Unfiltered samples for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, TP, cyto, lugols, tot metals; filtered nuts	34.8
KB3	PolarCirkel	24/07/23	30	78° 57.295	11° 57.134	Unfiltered samples for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, TP, cyto, lugols, tot metals; filtered nuts	34.6
KB6	PolarCirkel	25/07/23	48	78° 55.792	12° 23.146	Unfiltered samples for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, TP, cyto, lugols, tot metals; filtered nuts	34.7
KB6	PolarCirkel	25/07/23	30	78° 55.792	12° 23.146	Unfiltered samples for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, TP, cyto, lugols, tot metals; filtered nuts	34.2
KB6	PolarCirkel	25/07/23	5	78° 55.792	12° 23.146	Unfiltered samples for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, TP, cyto, lugols, tot metals; filtered nuts	31.5
KB7	PolarCirkel	25/07/23	60	78° 57.985	12° 22.798	Unfiltered samples for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, TP, cyto, lugols, tot metals; filtered nuts	34.7
KB7	PolarCirkel	25/07/23	30	78° 57.985	12° 22.798	Unfiltered samples for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, TP, cyto, lugols, tot metals; filtered nuts	34.1
KB7	PolarCirkel	25/07/23	5	78° 57.985	12° 22.798	Unfiltered samples for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, TP, cyto, lugols, tot metals; filtered nuts	31.4
KB1	Teisten	27/07/23	340	79° 00.701	11° 25.602	Unfiltered samples for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, TP, cyto, lugols, tot metals; filtered nuts	34.8
KB1	Teisten	27/07/23	200	79° 00.701	11° 25.602	Unfiltered samples for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, TP, cyto, lugols, tot metals; filtered nuts	34.9
KB1	Teisten	27/07/23	30	79° 00.701	11° 25.602	Unfiltered samples for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, TP, cyto, lugols, tot metals; filtered nuts	34.7
KB1	Teisten	27/07/23	5	79° 00.701	11° 25.602	Unfiltered samples for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, TP, cyto, lugols, tot metals; filtered nuts	32.7
KB8	Teisten	27/07/23	30	78° 52.772	12° 31.067	Unfiltered samples for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, TP, cyto, lugols, tot metals; filtered nuts	31.9
KB8	Teisten	27/07/23	5	78° 52.772	12° 31.067	Unfiltered samples for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, TP, cyto, lugols, tot metals; filtered nuts	34.2